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Research Article

DETERMINATION OF THE DEGREE OF EVIDENCE OF THE DISSEMINATION OF SPINE MEDICINE: STANDARD OF SPINE SURGERY STUDY

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Abstract:

Aim: The motivation behind our review is to determine the degree of evidence (LOE) of the dissemination of spine medicine, what is more, to contrast it with the level of world writing in spine medicine, and to decide the remainder of the academic development with that of the world-wide one.

Methods: An internet search using "PubMed" and "Google Scholar" was conducted using search words associated with the spine medical practice, such as "Spine medical procedure," "Scoliosis," "Herniated plate." Our current research was conducted from May 2019 to February 2020. Each paper was analyzed and evaluated by two researchers using the Oxford Center for Evidence-Based Medicine Evidence Levels.

Results: We distinguished 439 papers that met the requirements of incorporation; 57% were Level IV inquiries. Case accounts (43 per cent) became the most well-known method of inquiry. The number of nations with spine-medical distributions was 18. The country with the highest rate of dissemination was Egypt (29%). The number of transmitted exams rose from 156 in (2000–2008) to 287 in (2009–2015). Measurable essentiality occurs between high and low LOE publications ($p = 0.0008$).

Conclusion: We have shown that LOE has not improved entirely over the last 17 years and that a large portion of the distributions is low LOE (levels III and IV). In this regard, we stress the need for spine specialists in the countries to perform higher LOE investigations.

Keywords: spine, surgery, standards.

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INTRODUCTION:

With today's huge advances in data innovation, the enormous amount of clinical data has exploded, presenting a test to the clinical expert of how is the legitimate method of coordinating this data in clinical practice [1]. In addition, the requirement for a basic cycle for clinicians to evaluate and gather data from logic mining has grown, causing the improvement of evidence-based medicine (EBM), which has become fundamental in assessing the nature of distributed testing [2]. As far as is known, there has been no examination that evaluates the Arabic distributions in spinal medical procedures and decides the level of evidence for them [3]. We admit that the loss of effectiveness of Arabic distributions in spinal medical procedures has not evolved much to reach the standard level of global distributions due to some factors that will be mentioned later [4]. The purpose of our review is to evaluate the loss of efficiency of the Arab spine medical procedures in few countries of world and compare it to the world standard of spine medical procedures and to the different strengths, in order to decide whether the scientific creation of the world is maintained compared to that of the world [5].

METHODOLOGY:

This survey was conducted between May 2019 to February 2020. A survey procedure was produced for the recovery of all items related to spinal surgery. This investigation was carried out by going to information bases and using the accompanying convention: "Search term" and, in addition, "Name of the nation". Our current research was conducted from May 2019 to February 2020. The edited compositions were screened, and assuming that all standards of consideration were met, the full text was then obtained for more data. Eligibility rules for this study were all clinical articles related to spinal medical procedures published in English or French with English theoretical writing between January 2000 and June 2015. In addition, the principal investigator had to be

associated with an institution located in a nation, and the populations of these investigations, which were controlled or enrolled, had to be in an association located in an nation. The rules of avoidance were all articles that handled creature examinations, corpse examinations, basic sciences, investigations and articles. In addition, clinical examinations that were distributed before January 2010 were also excluded. Several elements were collected in each article selected for the survey, including journal name, Oscillation Factor (IF), year of distribution, alliance, nation, study plan, LOE, reference numbers, and information base. For individual diaries, we collected the 2015 Oscillation Factor for each diary. Note that some articles were distributed in diaries that were closed before 2015, so the wobble factor corresponding to the most recent year of distribution of these diaries was included. These items have been collected in the Excel accounting page. After the evaluation of each item, the side effect of the review was examined using a few boundaries like those distributed in another survey, namely the nation, as such, the nation with the highest number of distributions contrasting with the distributions of the rest of the nations. In addition, distributions in the period 2000-2008 were compared with distributions in the period 2009-2015; diary items distributed in diaries with a high effect factor (EF) were analyzed with distributions distributed in different diaries with a low or zero EF; searches with a high level of job loss (levels I and II) were compared with searches with a low level of job loss (levels III, IV and V). Microsoft Excel was used for the measurable study. Proportions of focal propensity, such as mean and median, were used for most boundaries, as well as filiation. Each pair of information in this survey was designed using the *F* test. A $p < 0.06$ and certainty duration were considered statistically critical. A Kappa score was determined to decide the level of understanding between the two commentators.

Figure 1:

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the review process

Figure 2:

RESULTS:

Out of 2358 digests screened, only 445 articles distributed between 2000 and 2019 meet the incorporation patterns of this study. The others were avoided because of their inability to meet the qualification rules of this examination (Figure 1). The strength of understanding between the two analysts was choice (Kappa = 0.909). The loss of interest in the papers of this examination is as follows: 0.47% Level I, 3.94% Level II, 37.1% Level III, 56.54% Level IV,

in addition, 2.99% Level V (Figure 2). The study design most generally experienced in the information from our review was case reports: 183 (42.72%), followed by planned surveys: 119 (27.28%), followed by planned reviews: 79 (18.52%), followed by planned cases: 41 (9.99%), randomized controlled trials (RCTs): 11 (2.53%), cross-sectional reviews: 7 (1.39%), basic audit: 5 (0.93%), and case control: 5 (0.68%). The number of countries with the following distribution of medical interventions on the spine: 19

(figure 3): Egypt: 114 (26.27%), Morocco: 79 (18.20%), Saudi Arabia: 79 (18.53%), Tunisia: 55 (12.97%), Lebanon: 26 (6.00%), Jordan: 15 (3.46%), Kuwait: 13 (3.00%), Iraq: 12 (2.76%), Oman: 10 (2.30%), Sudan: 8 (1.84%), Qatar: 7 (1.61%), United Arab Emirates (UAE) : 6 (1.38%), Algeria: 5 (1.15%), Bahrain: 4 (0.92%), Yemen: 3 (0.69%), Syria: 2 (0.46%), Libya: 1 (0.23%) and Palestine: 1 (0.23%). It is highly likely that the number of diaries in this review is between 0.089 and 6.87 (range 1.426). 203 articles (29%) were distributed in diaries with an unrecorded FI. The number of diaries used for distribution was 143. The 10 most frequently used diaries were Pan Arab Journal of Neurosurgery: 41 (9.45%), European Spine Journal: 19 (4.38%), The Spine Journal: 19 (4.38%), Neurosciences (Riyadh): 14 (3.23%), Egyptian Journal of Nervous system science, Psychiatry and Neurosurgery: 12 (2.76%), Asian Spine Journal: 11 (2.53%),

Neurosurgery: 11 (2.53%), International Orthopedics: 12 (3.54%), Joint Bone Spine: 11 (2.53%), and the Saudi Medical Journal: 12 (3.54%). The 276 surplus articles (64.14%) were distributed in 133 miscellaneous newspapers. Most of the articles selected for this review (92%) concerned adults, but 8.99% concerned children. Articles written in English accounted for 96.63% (419) of the total number of articles, while French articles accounted for 5.5% (21). Article reference numbers ranged from 0 to 136 (middle 2); 178 (41.7%) articles had no recorded reference number. In addition, the relationship coefficient between LOE and reference numbers was 0.3 ($p = 0.0019$), while the relationship coefficient between IF diaries and reference numbers was 0.54 ($p = 0.00005$); Table 1 summarizes and reflects on various highlights of the findings hence.

Table 1:

Feature	Articles number	LOE n (%)					LOE mean	CI 95%	p value
		I	II	III	IV	V			
<i>Country</i>									
Egypt	114	0	8 (7%)	80 (70.2%)	24 (21.1%)	2 (1.8%)	3.18	(-2.01-8.91)	0.014 (S)
Other	320	2 (0.63%)	9 (2.8%)	81 (25.3%)	217 (67.8%)	11 (3.44%)	3.7		
<i>Year</i>									
2000-2008	151	0	4 (2.65%)	46 (30.46%)	97 (64.24%)	4 (2.65%)	3.67	(1.19-6.01)	0.18 (NS)
2009-2015	283	2 (0.71%)	13 (4.60%)	115 (40.64%)	144 (50.89%)	9 (3.18%)	3.51		
<i>IF</i>									
≥1	146	2 (1.37%)	8 (5.48%)	52 (35.62%)	82 (56.16%)	2 (1.37%)	3.51	(0.18-6.94)	0.08 (NS)
<1	288	0	9 (3.13%)	109 (37.85%)	159 (55.21%)	11 (3.82%)	3.6		
<i>Study LOE</i>									
High level (I, II)	19	2 (10.5%)	17 (89.5%)	0	0	0	1.89	(-7.04-12.58)	0.0007 (S)
Low level (I, IV, V)	415	0	0	160 (38.6%)	242 (58.3%)	13 (3.13%)	3.65		

IF: impact factor; LOE: level of evidence; S: significant; NS: not significant.

Table 2:

	LOE n (%)			
	II	III	IV	V
	8 (7%)	80 (70.2%)	24 (21.1%)	2 (1.8%)
	9 (2.8%)	81 (25.3%)	217 (67.8%)	11 (3.4%)
	4 (2.65%)	46 (30.46%)	97 (64.24%)	4 (2.65%)
	13 (4.60%)	115 (40.64%)	144 (50.89%)	9 (3.18%)
	8 (5.48%)	52 (35.62%)	82 (56.16%)	2 (1.37%)
	9 (3.13%)	109 (37.85%)	159 (55.21%)	11 (3.82%)
	17 (89.5%)	0	0	0
	0	160 (38.6%)	242 (58.3%)	13 (3.13%)

ficant; NS: not significant.

DISCUSSION:

The fundamental focus of the direction of this review was to assess the level and type of evidence of distributions of spinal medical procedures distributed by organizations (Figure 4). After applying the incorporation models of this ongoing survey, case reports, which provide an impotent level of evidence, were incorporated, accounting for 42.8% of all distributions [6]. Low-level surveys (Tier III, Tier IV, and Tier V) account for 38.2%, 56.6%, and 2.98%, separately ($p = 0.0009$). In addition, high level (Level I or Level II) surveys accounted for 0.6% and 5%, separately ($p = 0.0009$) [7]. Comparing the sequelae of our review with a few Saudi reviews, which managed the loss of efficacy of Saudi distributions in the neurosurgery and muscle health territories, we found that the Level IV documents established by far the majority of these reviews, which is predictable with the results obtained from our information [8]. Looking at the reference numbers and their relationship to the LOE, one would expect articles with high LOE to have high reference numbers [9], however our review showed that there is a powerless negative relationship between the two ($r = -0.13$) ($p = 0.0019$). On the other hand, there is a fairly strong positive relationship between diary IF and reference number ($r = 0.54$) ($p = 0.00005$) [10].

CONCLUSION:

To address these issues and accelerate the pace of distributions, we need to manage the problems from different sides: from the clinical experts' side and from the side of society in general. As far as the experts are concerned, the idea of exploration too, EBM should be presented as far in advance as the drug staff, giving an early introduction to thinking about the meaning of such an idea. Preparing people for the review system and propelling and offering remuneration for such acts would greatly influence the quality and pace of distributions. Senior physicians (specialists) should be encouraged to do basic audits and meta-investigations on randomized preliminaries, as they are not exorbitant and take less time, and they almost provide the highest level of evidence.

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